

INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY AS THE MAIN FACTOR OF LEARNING EFFICIENCY

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Abstract. *One of the main tasks of the education system is to train and educate free-thinking, creative, active and all-round highly qualified personnel based on modern educational programs. Only a creative, professional teacher with high pedagogical skills, armed with modern innovative technologies can train such a pupil or student. In this sense, this article is also directly devoted to the issues of directing teachers to innovative activities.*

Keywords: *innovation, educational system, continuous education, stages of education, system of innovative activities, orientation of teachers to innovative activities.*

In the educational process of the Republic of Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to the training of ambitious personnel who can think independently and creatively, strive for creativity. It is known that in all eras, the subject of teaching, the educational system has developed in harmony with social development. All the social changes that have taken place are reflected in the content of education to a certain extent. This can also be seen in the example of the application of changes in the fields of science, technology and technology to the teaching process. One of the urgent tasks is to train young people in vocational subjects, to develop their inclination to study, to develop their abilities, knowledge and skills, to acquire their chosen professions, and to effectively organize their independent and creative work.

Our republic needs specialists with comprehensive thinking in various fields. How urgent this issue is today is confirmed by the following comments of our President Sh.M. Mirziyoev: "Today's rapidly changing world opens up new and great opportunities for humanity and young people".

The flow of information enters the social life of our republic at a rapid speed and covers a wide range. Receiving information at a rapid pace, analyzing, processing, theoretically summarizing, summarizing and delivering it to the student is one of the urgent problems facing the educational system. The application of pedagogical technology to the educational process serves to positively solve the above-mentioned actual problem.

By essence, innovation is considered a dynamic system of innovation in an attitude or process. Innovation as a system in itself represents the relationship or process, firstly, the internal logic, and secondly, the consistent development of the introduced innovation in a certain period of time and its interaction with the environment.

Therefore, today it is important to carry out the activities of every sector and system on the basis of innovative ideas and technologies. In this regard, before entering the topic, we found it necessary to dwell a little on the meaning of the word "innovation".

The concept of innovation (Latin novus-new) was used in research and scientific work in the 19th century. First, it represented the introduction of individual elements from one field to another. By learning the rules of introducing technical innovations, firms have adopted "innovation policy" as a whole system for profit. This activity has general features, rules, and a mechanism for updating the voluntary part of society's life.

V. A. Slastenin², one of our famous pedagogic scientists, considers innovation to be a set of purposeful, directed actions aimed at creating, spreading and using new things. In his opinion, any innovation aims to satisfy the needs of social subjects and stimulate their aspirations with the help of new tools.

The concepts of "new" and "innovation" are important in any innovation. The novelty introduced into various attitudes and processes is manifested in the form of private, subjective, local and conditional ideas.

In the same sense, R. N. Yusufbekova³ also focuses on considering innovations from a pedagogical point of view. In particular, it is emphasized by the author that pedagogical innovations are the content of a pedagogical phenomenon that may change, leading to a previously unknown, unrecorded situation or result in the process of education and upbringing.

According to V.A. Slastenin, an innovative approach means having:

- creative activity;
- technological and methodological preparation for innovation (change) in activity;
- new thinking;
- high culture of treatment.

The ultimate goal of the concept of "Innovative approach" emerging in modern educational development is to introduce changes and updates that guarantee the result of the educational process in the field of education.

Pedagogical innovations are used in order to make positive changes in the relevant field and achieve high-quality results. The grounding of this type of innovation takes place in certain stages

They are:

Today, the main focus of the education system is to train thinking, creative, active and high-performing personnel.

Therefore, one of the main tasks of the educational system is to train and educate free-thinking, creative, active and highly qualified personnel based on modern educational programs. Only a creative, professional teacher with high pedagogical skills, armed with modern innovative technologies can train such a pupil or student.

It should be noted that the following important tasks are set before the teachers: implementation of active forms of education, modernization of teaching practice, application of flexible, variable, innovative teaching technologies, like all forms of education. An innovative approach in the educational system means a set of pedagogical technology improvement processes, methods, methods and training manuals.

It is known that any modern technology or innovations serve to increase the efficiency of educational activity based on the purposeful, meaningful, specific capabilities of the taught subject, and ultimately make the student an active subject of education. Modern pedagogical technologies create a non-standard approach to the educational process, that is, create subject-subject relations. As a result, the student's personality and individual characteristics come to the fore. It is also important that self-education and self-development are emphasized in the implementation of these technologies.

The essence of the system of innovative training of teachers is to harmonize its traditional and new technologies based on innovative laws.

Innovation is a complex interdisciplinary process. This process is carried out in the form of a live dialogue between the teacher and the student in modern educational activities, and the personality of the teacher and the student plays a key role in it.

Modeling teacher training is aimed at a certain goal, which is the result of a number of contradictions. From this point of view, the teacher training model consists of republican and regional components. The national components consist of basic guidelines, while the regional components consist of a body of professional knowledge.

The contextual approach is one of the priority innovation directions. On its basis, the integration of students' educational and professional activities is realized.

The modern teacher training model developed by us lays the groundwork for the creation of textbooks on primary education methodology, which should be able to meet new didactic requirements.

New textbooks must be adapted to didactic changes.

Tasks with the nature of classification are created taking into account the level of preparation and talent of the student.

Abroad, the contextual system developed by A.L. Verbitsky is recognized as a generalized method. In the conditions of contextual education, the student is formed as a specialist on the one hand, and as a member of society, that is, a certain ethno-cultural or regional entity, on the other.

In our opinion, modeling should be carried out mainly in three directions:

1. Object modeling.
2. Basic characters and contexts.
3. Modeling according to the situation.

In the process of professional education, we analyzed regional and pedagogical knowledge, paying special attention to the regional context. They are called progressive-operational and socio-regional.

The first group includes factors such as selection of ethno-regional teaching material, building on accumulated knowledge and practice, use of ethno-regional material and improvement of results.

The second group includes activities such as classification, individualization, determination of a person's mental state and orientation in communication with students in an ethnocultural environment.

Among the methods we recommend in the implementation of the regional orientation process, social communication with students should be highlighted. Exercises called "Masquerade", "Carnival", "Association" are performed in the form of dialogue, cooperation, poetic spiritual retreats and include proverbs, regional games, riddles, songs and jokes.

All these are the main ways of regionalization of innovative teacher training.

Another form that reflects modern educational trends is game technologies. Aspects characterizing the game include its emotionality, problemativeness, symbolism, intellectuality, collectiveness. The game is constantly absorbed from the educational process to the quasi-professional, educational-professional and professional process.

The game affects the personal behavior of students as an external stimulus and driving force, and the lessons conducted with the help of game methods help students to reveal the content of professional work along with mastering the science of primary education methodology.

The physical, mental and social aspects of a person can be listed as the main driving force of the game.

With the help of students, together with the author, the following types of games were developed:

- object-picture games;
- games designed to expand the concepts of existence;
- artistic games;
- creative games.

The novelty of the recommended game technologies is that they have an artistic-symbolic character, they are based on factors such as the integration of graphic activities, the emotional content of the teaching process, the creation of a ground for creative cooperation, humanism, and mutual relations. The results of questionnaires conducted with students during the experiment show that students are interested in the news and believe in its effectiveness.

In the process of pedagogical practice, students showed examples of professional skills, activity, positive motivation and ability to work with children.

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